

Production of integrated rice culture and aquaculture on saline coastal soils in West Bengal, India, 1982.

Production (t/ha)	
Summer fallow period Apr- Jun 1982	Kharif, Sep-Nov 1982
	CSR1 3.12
	SR26 B 3.20
	Assam (S) 2.88
Brackish water 0.65 fish and prawn	Freshwater fish and prawn 0.51

to 24 mmho/cm (see figure).

After the aquaculture harvest, monsoon precipitation (av 1,750 mm/yr, of which 80% occurs from Jun to Sep) lowered soil salinity through runoff and leaching. However, late, low precipitation during 1982 delayed soil desalinization. E_{Ce} had dropped to 7 mmho/cm by Aug, when one-month-old seedlings of CSR1, SR26B, and Assam (S) were transplanted in each plot. Standard cultivation practices were followed. As the monsoon continued, E_{Ce} declined to an average between 4.8 and 5.8 mmho/cm for the rice

growing season. During the rice season, plots were used to grow some freshwater fishes and prawns (*L. rohita*, *C. catla*, *C. mrigala*, *H. molitrix*, and *M. rosenbargii*), stocked at 23,500/ha.

Rice was harvested in late Nov 1982. Average yield was 3.1 t/ha. Fishes and prawns, harvested at the same time, yielded 0.5 t/ha after 83 d of growth (see table).

Integrating brackish and freshwater aquaculture with rice culture on saline coastal soils yielded 1.16 t fish and prawn/ha and did not reduce rice yield. □

Nitrogen requirement of rice nurseries

M. S. Maskina and O. P. Meelu, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

Recent experiments show that modern varieties can be transplanted, without yield loss, as late as 60 d after nursery establishment, or about 30 d older than is generally recommended. Maintaining nurseries for that length of time brings increased fertilizer requirements. We studied the nitrogen requirements of rice nurseries at PAU farm in 1981 and 1982.

Soil was loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 8.4; low organic carbon. 0.23%; and 87-8-86 kg available NPK/ha. Nitrogen was applied as urea at 60, 90, or 120 kg/ha in 3 equal splits: at sowing, and at 15 and 30 d after sowing. Ten kg P

and 15 t farmyard manure/ha were applied basally. Nurseries were grown on 10- x 2-m beds planted with 1 kg seed. Nursery health was evaluated visually and by measuring seedling height and dry matter production.

Ninety and 120 kg N/ha produced better growth and healthier seedlings, but results of those 2 treatments did not differ.

Forty-five-day-old seedlings grown at different nitrogen levels were evaluated for yield. Seedlings were transplanted and received recommended doses of 120-26-25 kg NPK/ha. Data show that the nursery grown with 90 kg N/ha yielded 600-700 more rice than the nursery that received 60 kg N/ha (see figure). Yields for 90 and 120 kg N/ha did not differ. □

Effect on rice yield of N levels applied to the nursery, 1981-82.

Folcystein as a biostimulant in rice production

J. L. Armenta-Soto, national coordinator for lowland rice, P. O. Box 356, Culiacan Sin, Mexico 80-000

We evaluated the yield biostimulant folcystein, derived from L-cystein with 50 g ai/liter and 1.0 g folic acid/liter, for drilled lowland rice at Culiacan Experiment Station (CAEVACU), Mexico. A foliar spray of folcystein was applied 80 d after seeding (1 wk after panicle initiation) at concentrations of 0, 200, 400, 500, 800, and 1000 ml/ha, equivalent to 50 mg ai/ml derived from L-cystein and 1 mg folic acid/ml, in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

Table 1. Effect of different levels of folcystein on rice yield, 1976.

Folcystein (ml/ha)	Treatment mean ^a (t/ha)
400	7.2 a
800	6.1 a
1000	5.8 a
600	5.0 b
200	4.9 b
0	4.8 b

^aAv of 3 replications. Any two means having a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. S \bar{x} = 496.95

Plots were 4.5 m² with five 6-m rows with 25 cm within-row spacing. Local variety Bamoa A75, with 130 d duration, was seeded at 80 kg/ha. Urea 46%, N was

Table 2. Doses and timing of application of folcystein, treatment mean, and statistical significance, 1982.

Doses (ml/ha) and timing of application ^a	Treatment no.	Treatment mean ^b (t/ha)
400 E ₁	3	5.9 a
200 E ₁	2	5.7 ab
200 E ₂	7	5.6 ab
400 E ₂	8	5.5 ab
600 E ₁	4	5.3 b
800 E ₂	10	5.2 b
600 E ₂	9	5.1 b
0.0 E ₁	1	5.1 b
0.0 E ₂	6	5.1 b
800 E ₁	5	5.0 c

^aE₁ = maximum tillering (45 days after seeding [DS]); E₂ = panicle initiation (75 DS). ^bAv of three replications. Any two means having a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. S \bar{x} = 189.5 kg.

broadcast at 100 kg N/ha 35 d after seeding (DS) and at 50 kg N/ha 65 DS.

A second evaluation of folcystein in summer 1982 tested doses of 0, 200, 400, 600, and 800 ml/ha, applied at maximum tillering and at panicle initiation. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plot size was 4.5 m². Local recommended variety Culiacan A82 (135 d duration)

was seeded at 140 kg/ha. Nitrogen fertilization was the same as in the first trial.

In the first trial, the 400 ml dose increased yield the most (Table 1). Analysis of variance showed there were statistical differences between doses (D), and non-significant difference for timing of application (E) and the interaction D × E, for the second trial. The indication is that folcystein could be applied at any of the

two times. Three statistical groups were formed based on Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Table 2).

Although treatments 3, 2, 7, and 8 belong to the same group, in terms of yield and income after subtracting cost of the product and aerial application, the dose of 400 ml/ha at E₁ is the best choice, and is an effective yield stimulator. □

Environment and its influence

Seasonal influence and effect of growth regulators on rice spikelet sterility

P. S. S. Murthy, plant physiologist, NARP Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru 5341 22, West Godavari Disirict, AP; and K. S. Murty, Central Rice Research Institute (CRR), Cuttack 753006, India

We studied the influence of seasons and growth regulators on spikelet sterility in rice *Oryza sativa* L. in field trials at CRR in 1977 rabi and kharif. Four modern rice varieties — Ratna, Pusa 2-21, Pallavi, and IET2233 — were grown in three replications in a split-plot design.

The following were applied as a foliar spray to the whole plant 3 d after anthesis: auxin H-61 (1:2000 concentration), 2,4-D (100 ppm), GA-3 (100 ppm), kinetin (100 ppm), and control (distilled water spray). The crop was grown under normal fertilization — 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha. Irrigation and plant protection were

Effect of growth regulators on spikelet sterility of 4 rices, 1977, Cuttack, India.^a

Treatment	Sterility (%)							
	Ratna		Pusa 2-21		Pallavi		IET2233	
	K	R	K	R	K	R	K	R
Control	40.5	24.5	35.4	18.4	28.4	12.3	30.2	14.8
Auxin H-61	39.9	18.6	35.6	20.4	26.8	14.0	31.4	16.0
2,4-D	36.9	20.4	34.6	19.7	27.9	13.0	30.4	15.4
GA	41.5	24.6	36.2	19.7	29.1	13.1	31.8	15.3
Kinetin	26.3	16.7	26.4	16.8	20.9	10.4	25.4	12.7
Mean	37.4	21.7	34.2	19.0	26.9	12.9	30.0	15.1
			V	G	VG			
			K	R	K	R	K	R
SEM +			1.01	0.46	1.18	1.11	2.10	2.22
CD 5%			3.20	1.12	2.43	2.24	NS	4.49
CD 1%			5.88	1.71	3.28	3.00	NS	6.00

^aK = kharif (wet), R = rabi (dry), V = variety, G = growth regulators.

supplied when necessary.

Spikelet sterility was 92% higher in kharif than in rabi for the 4 varieties (see table). Ratna and Pusa 2-21 had higher sterility than IET2233 and Pallavi in both

seasons.

Kinetin significantly reduced spikelet sterility of all varieties in both seasons and was significantly superior to other growth regulators. □

Announcements

IRRI-Tanzania sign technical and scientific cooperation agreement

The Government of Tanzania and IRRI have signed a memorandum of understanding that calls for a 5-year program of scientific and technical cooperation.

The objective is to enhance Tanzania's capabilities for research on rice and rice-based cropping systems. Priority will be on genetic evaluation and utilization of

rice varieties appropriate to Tanzanian rice growing areas, development of improved rice-based farming systems to increase land use intensity and extend the rice growing area, training of Tanzanian scientists, and development and testing of appropriate machinery for small-scale farming.

Collaborative activities under the program will be based upon mutually agreed upon 2-year work plans to be developed

by the Tanzanian Ministry of Agriculture and IRRI. Research, training, and rice production programs are priority items in the initial work plan. □

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